

Maumee River Floodplain Project, Henry County (41.41480, -84.03070)

Since construction in 2023, the Maumee River Floodplain (also known as Rotary Riverside Preserve Restoration) Project’s primary known nutrient benefit has been its runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source, preventing approximately 0.8 lbs phosphorus export per acre each year. Low rainfall conditions in 2024 likely limited the newly delivered nutrients to the Project, which limits the total capacity for the Project to filter and retain nutrients. However, the Project functions as a floodplain wetland in wetter conditions and can even receive extensive seasonal flooding, as researchers observed during an initial site visit in early 2023, suggesting potential for meaningful nutrient inputs in future years.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project has 35 acres of restored wetland and consists of a single large central wetland, three northern pools of varying depths (one of which was constructed to meet habitat needs of a specific endangered fish), and many hummock-hollow pools in the southwest area. The large central wetland acts as an occasional floodplain pool. The smaller pools normally act as depressional wetlands but also receive water from the Maumee or existing oxbow wetland at very high water levels. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm event in which the Maumee River floods the central pool via the existing oxbow wetland.

Nutrient Retention

Converted Farmland Area	Phosphorus Loss Prevented Annually	
	Per Acre	Total (Mean ± SD)
35 acres	0.8 lbs	46 ± 26 lbs

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in similar floodplain wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Enlarging the central wetland pool would increase the Project’s holding capacity for water and ensure that nutrient rich water does not leave the site.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.